

BEHAVIOR OF GFRP BARS SUBJECTED TO DYNAMIC LOADING

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ABSTRACT

The use of Fiber Reinforced Polymer (FRP) bars in concrete structures has grown appreciably in the last few years. FRP bars increase the service life of structures as they overcome the corrosion problem of steel reinforcement. The objective of this paper is to study the behaviour of Glass FRP (GFRP) bars subjected to impact loading using the drop hammer test. The tests were conducted on GFRP specimens with different nominal diameters at various loading rates. Experimental results showed that as loading rate increases the strength of bars increases except bars with a nominal diameter of 17 mm where the average stress decreases at higher rates. All the bars failed due to the separation of the fibers.

1 INTRODUCTION

Fiber Reinforced Polymer (FRP) bars have emerged as a practical substitute for steel rebars in concrete structures. FRP bars, non-corrodible by nature, are most commonly used in harsh corrosive environments such as marine structures and bridges. Other attractive properties of FRP bars include high strength to weight ratio and magnetic transparency. In recent years, extensive research conducted on FRP bars lead to noteworthy advancements in this field. For instance, Abed and his co-workers [1-3] examined the bond durability of sand-coated Basalt FRP (BFRP) bars under tension. The study compared the tensile behavior of different bar types (glass and basalt) exposed to conditioning environment such as salt and alkaline for various periods (30, 60, 90 days). The results showed that BFRP bars exhibited better bond strength and adhesion than the Glass FRP (GFRP) bars. Nevertheless, other factors which influenced the bond strength were the absorption of the bar and quality of manufacturing. Conditioning showed a negligible effect on the slip of the FRP bars. Moreover, El Refai, Abed and Al-Rahmani [4-5] investigated the structural properties of hybrid reinforced concrete beams. The study deduced that the use of both steel and GFRP rebars improved the flexural performance of the concrete beams, but beams still failed as a result of GFRP bars' rupture. Furthermore, Abed, El-Chabib, and AlHamaydeh [6] loaded GFRP reinforced concrete beams up to failure and evaluated their ultimate shear capacity and load-deformation relationships. The beams, particularly those with large shear capacities, displayed great deformation at their ultimate load then instantaneously failed.

However, uncertainty about the behavior of FRP bars in compression still exists. Current design guidelines neglect the compressive contribution of FRP bars in concrete members due to insufficient data and doubts regarding the performance of FRP bars in compression, see the recent literature review analysis on the use of FRP in concrete under compression in [7].

Several recent studies were carried out to understand the behavior of FRP bars in compression [8-16]. For example, Deitz, Harik, and Gesund [8] evaluated the compressive properties of forty-five GFRP rebars. Various unbraced lengths of the rebars were utilized to obtain the physical properties for

a range of slenderness ratios. Test results showed that for non-slender rebars, with unbraced lengths less than 110 mm, the ultimate compressive strength is almost half of the ultimate tensile strength. Young modulus in compression, as well as tension, was approximately equivalent to 42.5 GPa. Khan, Sheikh and Hadi [9] tested and compared Glass FRP (GFRP) and Carbon FRP (CFRP) bars in tension and compression. The compression tests were conducted by applying a loading rate of 1.0 to 1.3mm per minute and placing steel plates at both loading heads of the Universal Testing Machine (UTM). Analysis of results showed that GFRP bars achieved greater stress and strain than CFRP bars in both tension and compression. The tensile ultimate strength and modulus of elasticity of the FRP bars were reported to be 1.67 and 1.59 times higher than in compression respectively. The elastic modulus of GFRP bars had a value of 42 GPa. Plevkov, Baldin, Kudyakov, and Nevskii [10] examined the mechanical properties of CFRP and GFRP bars. Longitudinal deformation of the bars under compressive load was measured. CFRP bars reported lower elastic modulus and ultimate strength than GFRP bars in tension and compression. The elastic modulus and ultimate strength of GFRP bars in compression were evaluated as 41040 MPa and 788 MPa respectively.

Khorrarnian and Sadeghian [11] investigated the response of fifteen GFRP bars in compression. The test method included the use of steel caps at both ends of each bar to prevent the bar from premature failure. Results showed that the compressive properties of GFRP bars which consist of ultimate strength, modulus of elasticity and strain were comparable to the tensile properties. The study concluded that disregarding the contribution of GFRP bars in compressive members is not practical. Fillmore and Sadeghian [12] examined the behavior of GFRP bars in compression and compared the compressive performance of concrete cylinders reinforced with GFRP and steel bars. The test program used the same approach as Khorrarnian et al. [11] to avoid buckling of the bars. The test results showed that the elastic modulus of GFRP bars in compression is similar to that in tension. The compressive strength, though, was about two-thirds of the tensile strength. The study concluded that ignoring the compressive contribution of GFRP bars in concrete members is not realistic.

Thiyagarajan, Pavalan, and Sivagamasundari [13] investigated the mechanical characteristics of Basalt FRP (BFRP) bars of different diameters. The compressive strength of the BFRP bars was in the range of 470.2 - 495.3 MPa which is almost 50% of the tensile strength. With the increase of the diameter, the compressive strength varied very slightly.

Bruun [14] studied the relationship between the length and the compressive strength of GFRP rebars. The investigation concluded that samples with unbraced lengths less than 230 mm failed due to pure crushing at a compressive strength of 730 MPa. On the other hand, longer specimens experienced failure due to global buckling and that the compressive strength decreased with the increase of unbraced length. Sheikh and Kharal [15] analyzed the behavior of GFRP rebars in Reinforced Concrete Structures. The compression tests were carried out on GFRP specimens of various unbraced lengths. The investigation deduced that for an unbraced length of 230 mm, the observed compressive strength value was 730 MPa. The elastic modulus in tension and compression was found to be 60 GPa.

Chulia, Concepcion, Cano, and Soler [16] analyzed GFRP reinforced concrete elements in compression and developed an analytical model that considered the compressive strength of GFRP bars. The average compressive strength and modulus of elasticity of the rebars were determined as 318.7 MPa and 42000 MPa respectively. The investigation deduced that the design codes of concrete structures should take into consideration the compressive contribution of GFRP bars. Both compressive properties of the bar, ultimate strength and elastic modulus, increased when the diameter decreased.

To the best of the researcher's knowledge, there is a lack of studies on the response of FRP bars to impact loading. This paper aims to investigate the behavior of GFRP bars of different diameters subjected to impact loads. By conducting drop hammer tests, the maximum strength of the bars will be determined for different loading rates.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

2.1 MATERIAL PROPERTIES

The experimental program consisted of twenty-one GFRP bars with different nominal diameters (12, 17, 20, 27 mm). The GFRP bars were manufactured and provided by Pultron Ltd company denoted as G0 and by Galen company denoted as G1. Tables 1- 4 provide details of the diameter and length of the GFRP bars and report the dynamic testing results of the specimens.

Loading Rate (1/s)	Specimen Number	Length (mm)	Diameter (mm)	Impact Energy (J)	Maximum Stress (MPa)
180	S1	34	17.4	469	640.3
	S2	34	17.4	469	581.0
	S3	34	17.4	469	455.9
				Average	559.1
				Standard Deviation	94.1
222	S4	34	17.4	471	317.3
	S5	34	17.4	471	232.8
	S6	34	17.4	471	251.8
				Average	267.3
				Standard Deviation	44.3

Table 1: Details and Dynamic Results of G1-D17

Loading Rate (1/s)	Specimen Number	Length (mm)	Diameter (mm)	Impact Energy (J)	Maximum Stress (MPa)
180	S1	41	21.1	907.0	249.1
	S2	41	21.1	907.0	367.4
	S3	41	21.1	907.0	230.1
				Average	282.2
				Standard Deviation	74.4
222	S4	41	21.1	898.6	326.8
	S5	41	21.1	898.6	408.9
	S6	41	21.1	898.6	239.8
				Average	325.2
				Standard Deviation	84.6

Table 2: Details and Dynamic Results of G1-D20

Loading Rate (1/s)	Specimen Number	Length (mm)	Diameter (mm)	Impact Energy (J)	Maximum Stress (MPa)
166	S1	26.6	12.6	245.3	384.5
	S2	26.6	12.6	245.3	323.3
	S3	26.6	12.6	245.3	326.3
	S4	26.6	12.6	245.3	371.0
	S5	26.6	12.6	245.3	431.3
				Average	367.3
				Standard Deviation	44.8

Table 3: Details and Dynamic Results of G1-D12

Loading Rate (1/s)	Specimen Number	Length (mm)	Diameter (mm)	Impact Energy (J)	Maximum Stress (MPa)
140	S1	54.4	27.2	673.9	344.6
	S2	54.4	27.2	673.9	339.9
				Average	342.2
				Standard Deviation	3.4
163	S3	54.4	27.2	898.6	319.0
	S4	54.4	27.2	898.6	346.0
				Average	332.5
				Standard Deviation	19.1

Table 4: Details and Dynamic Results of G0-D27

2.2 TEST SETUP

The impact load tests were conducted using a drop hammer test. The GFRP bars were kept on a drop mass bench with a free end and the other end slightly clamped by artificial clay. The test arrangement consisted of a dynamic load cell, a 5000 g accelerometer, and a laser beam displacement transducer. Force and displacement data were recorded simultaneously by linking the devices to an acquisition chain. Two photocells were used to synchronize the obtained data. The GFRP bar specimens were subjected to drop hammer impacts in which the potential energy changes to kinetic energy. To achieve different impact velocities, the weight of the mass and height of the fall were varied. The experimental setup for the dynamic tests is depicted in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Experimental Setup of the Impact Load Tests using Dynamic Drop Mass Bench

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The effect of different rates of loading on the ultimate stress of the GFRP bars is shown in the confidence interval graphs in Fig. 2. The observed failure modes of the tested specimens are depicted in Fig. 3. As the rate of loading increased, the ultimate strength of the G1-D17 bars dropped (Fig. 2a) while the mean stress of the G1-D20 bars showed an increase (Fig. 2b). All G0-D27 specimens reported similar mean stress values as the loading rate increased from 140 to 163 s⁻¹ (Fig. 2d).

Figure 2: Confidence Interval Graphs of a) G1-D17 b) G1-D20 c) G1-D12 d) G0-D27

It is noted that for G0-D27 and G1-D17, the shape of the bars changed from cylindrical to conical (Fig. 3a and 3d). For G1-D20, the test specimens were crushed completely (Fig. 3b). Overall, the GFRP bars failed due to the separation of the fibers.

Figure 3: Failure Modes of a) G1-D17 b) G1-D20 c) G1-D12 d) G0-D27

4 CONCLUSIONS

This paper reported brief summary of part of the results for a larger experimental program to investigate the behavior of GFRP bars subjected to impact loading. The impact tests were conducted on GFRP bars using the drop hammer test at various loading rates. The test results showed that upon increasing the loading rate, the maximum strength of G1-D17 bar group decreased unlike most of the other bar types and diameters. Such behavior require further investigation and more tests are deemed necessary for solid conclusions. The general failure modes of GFRP bars were the separation of fibers where the G1-D20 bars were entirely crushed.

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